

Supplementary file 4

In this supplement, we provide an overview of web resources and databases that can be used to gather information needed for assessments.

Recommended Resources

Category	Resource	Link	Purpose
Gene expression	Ensembl	http://www.ensembl.org/	Database with annotation of genes and their isoform diversity on the genome.
	GTE _x (Genotype-Tissue Expression Project)	https://www.gtexportal.org/home/	Provides comprehensive data on gene expression and regulation across multiple human tissues.
	Human Protein Atlas	https://www.proteinatlas.org/	Maps protein expression across tissues and organs using antibody-based and transcriptomic data.
	Brain Span	https://www.brainspan.org/	A resource for studying transcriptional mechanisms involved in human brain development.
Gene–disease associations	OMIM (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man)	https://www.omim.org/	Authoritative catalog of human genes and genetic disorders,

			detailing genotype–phenotype relationships.
ClinGen (Clinical Genome Resource)	https://clinicalgenome.org/		Curates clinically relevant genes and variants to support genomic medicine and interpretation standards.
GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1116/		Expert-authored, peer-reviewed summaries of genetic conditions, including diagnosis and management.
Orphanet	https://www.orpha.net/		Comprehensive database for rare diseases and orphan drugs.
Human Gene Mutation Database (HGMD)	https://www.hgmd.cf.ac.uk/ac/index.php		Database with gene lesions responsible for human inherited disease.
Gene2Phenotype (G2P) / PanelApp	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gene2phenotype/; https://panelapp.genomicsengland.co.uk/panels/484/		Curated links between genes and phenotypes used to define diagnostic gene panels.

	Gene–Disease Validity Curation Process	PMID: 35266245	Describes standardized methods for assessing gene–disease relationship validity.
Practical guidelines	ACMG (American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics)	https://www.acmg.net/ACMG/Medical-Genetics-Practice-Resources/Practice-Guidelines.aspx	Provides clinical practice guidelines and standards for medical genetics and genomics.
	HGVS Nomenclature	https://hgvs-nomenclature.org/stable/	The standard for description of DNA, RNA, and protein sequence variants.
Variant databases	gnomAD (Genome Aggregation Database)	https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/	Aggregated population genetics data to assess variant frequency and constraint.
	DECIPHER	https://www.deciphergenomics.org/	Database for sharing and visualizing rare variant and phenotype data from clinical cases.
	UCSC Genome Browser	https://genome.ucsc.edu/	Comprehensive genome visualization platform integrating genomic

			annotations and datasets.
	COSMIC (Catalogue Of Somatic Mutations In Cancer)	https://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic/login	Database with the impact of somatic mutations in human cancer. Can be used when considering the safety/risk of upregulating genes.
Therapy databases	N1C Gene Registry	https://generegistry.n1collaborative.org/index.html	Registry of ultra-rare disease genes targeted by personalized antisense therapies.
	n-Lorem Available Therapies	https://www.nlorem.org/patients/active-gene-programs/	Lists gene programs supported by n-Lorem for free antisense therapies for nano-rare diseases.
	RX Genes	https://www.rx-genes.com/	Database linking genetic variants to potential therapeutic interventions.
	TreatabolomeDB	https://treatabolome.org	Curates evidence-based information on gene-disease-treatment relationships

			for rare diseases.
	RxMatcher	https://rxmatcher.org/	Tool to match molecular diagnoses with potential treatments based on curated data.
	Gene Therapy Trial Browser	https://scge.mcw.edu/platform/data/search/ClinicalTrial	Searchable database of gene therapy clinical trials curated by the Somatic Cell Genome Editing consortium.
	ClinicalTrials.gov	https://clinicaltrials.gov/	Database with clinical studies from around the world.
	ASGCT quarterly landscape reports	https://www.asgct.org/news-publications/landscape-report	Gives an overview of recent clinical trials and therapy approvals relating to gene and cell therapy.
	ClinGen Clinical Actionability Curations	https://www.clinicalgenome.org/curation-activities/clinical-actionability/browse-curations/	Provides information on gene-condition pairs that meet a clinical actionability threshold for pathogenic variants in the gene.

Patient education and health literacy support	UNIQUE	https://rarechromo.org/	Provides support, information, and networking for families affected by rare chromosome and gene disorders.
	Genetic and Rare Diseases Information Center (GARD)	https://rarediseases.info.nih.gov/	American center to help people with a rare disease access information, get a diagnosis, and find resources.
	RARE portal	https://www.rareportal.org.au/	Australia's resource for rare diseases.
	Advanced therapies handbook	https://www.schn.health.nsw.gov.au/advanced-therapies-handbook	A handbook that helps parents and caretakers understand some of the advanced therapies used to treat some rare conditions.